

Synthesis and Characterization of Lithium Dysprosium(III) Periodate

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Preparation of a new complex periodate of dysprosium(III) as $\text{Li}_7\text{Dy}(\text{IO}_6)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been described. Structural aspects of the complex are discussed from the results of chemical analysis, paper electrophoresis, thermal, magnetic, potentiometric, ir and diffused reflectance spectral studies.

COBALT²⁺, gold³⁺, silver³⁺, copper⁴⁺ and cerium⁴⁺ periodate compounds have already been prepared by various workers in this field. Simple periodates of some lanthanons have also been reported⁶. Complex periodate of dysprosium has not been reported so far. We report here the preparation of a new complex periodate of dysprosium(III) as $\text{Li}_7\text{Dy}(\text{IO}_6)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and its characterisation by chemical analysis, paper electrophoresis, thermal studies, magnetic measurements, equivalent weight determination, infrared spectra, diffused reflectance spectra and potentiometric titration. A probable structure of the periodate has also been proposed.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A. R. grade. Thermal analysis was carried out on a manual derivatograph. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, magnetic measurements were made on Gouy balance, electronics spectra were recorded on Cary 17 D spectrophotometer, and potentiometric measurements were made with a Philips potentiometer.

Preparation of lithium dysprosium periodate: Dysprosium nitrate (0.0057 mole) solution in water (25 ml) was added to KIO_4 (0.0043 mole) in KOH solution (3 N; 40 ml). The mixture was stirred for 3 hr at 60 to 70° and filtered through a sintered crucible. A colourless filtrate was obtained and an equivalent amount of lithium sulphate solution was added to the filtrate. A white precipitate of lithium dysprosium periodate was obtained which was filtered through a sintered crucible, washed with water to free it from alkali and other impurities, washed several times with ether and finally dried in a vacuum desiccator.

The compound is white in colour and insoluble in water. On the basis of chemical analysis, the compound has been given the composition $\text{Li}_7\text{Dy}(\text{IO}_6)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$. (Found: Li, 6.49; Dy, 22.78; I, 35.93; H_2O , 7.74. Calcd. for $\text{Li}_7\text{Dy}(\text{IO}_6)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$; Li, 6.79; Dy, 22.86; I, 35.77; H_2O , 7.59%).

Dysprosium was estimated gravimetrically⁷ as Dy_2O_3 . Iodine was analysed as AgI following the method of Willard and Furman⁸. Lithium was estimated by atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AA: 6). Water was determined by heating the sample at 140° for about 3 hr.

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF THERMOGRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS

Weight of the compounds (g)	Weight of the residue (g) Found	Analysis of the residue				
		%Li		%Dy		
	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	
0.0782	0.0325	0.0319	16.41	16.60	55.82	55.88

Results and Discussion

In the thermogravimetric analysis (Fig. 1), the compound first loses weight at 140° due to loss of water molecules (H_2O ; Found: 7.67; Calcd.: 7.59%). It begins to decompose at 180° and reaches constant weight at 540° to yield mixed oxides of lithium and dysprosium after the liberation of I_2 and O_2 . The colour of the residue is white. The results are given in Table 1. The compound decomposes as $2\text{Li}_7\text{Dy}(\text{IO}_6)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O} \longrightarrow 7\text{Li}_2\text{O} + \text{Dy}_2\text{O}_3 + 2\text{I}_2 + 7\text{O}_2 + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$

The ir spectrum of the compound in CsI (Fig. 2) shows a strong and broad band in the range 3360-3440 cm^{-1} due to $-\text{OH}$ stretching vibration while the band at 1640 cm^{-1} is due to bending mode of

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Fig. 1. TGA curve of $\text{Li}_7\text{Dy}(\text{IO}_6)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Fig. 3. Diffused reflectance spectra of $\text{Li}_7\text{Dy}(\text{IO}_6)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

H_2O . Hydrogen bonding of the type $-\text{OH} \cdots \text{O}$ is responsible for broadening of the band. However $\text{I}-\text{OH}$ and $\text{I}-\text{O}^9$ are observed at 1390 and $720-740 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively, $(\text{O}-\text{I}-\text{O})$ vibration at $420-460 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the grating vibration at $220-240 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Metal oxygen bonding may also be present in the lower region¹⁰.

The diffused reflectance spectrum of the compound (Fig. 3) does not show any absorption in the visible region. A broad band observed at 220 nm is due to the presence of IO_6^{2-} ion¹¹.

Magnetic susceptibility of the compound is 10.35 B.M. at 30° , and is consistent with the oxidation state¹² of dysprosium(III).

Equivalent weight was determined by the method of Lister and Yoshino¹³. A known amount of the compound dissolved in $2 \text{ N H}_2\text{SO}_4$ was treated with an excess of standard Mohr solution in $1 \text{ N H}_2\text{SO}_4$. The excess Mohr salt was titrated back at room temperature with standard $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ solution using barium diphenylamine sulphonate as indicator. 4.01 moles of Fe^{2+} were required per mole of the compound corresponding to the reduction of periodate to iodate by the reaction (1)

Another procedure was carried out by using standard sodium thiosulphate solution when a

Fig. 2. Infrared spectrum of $\text{Li}_7\text{Dy}(\text{IO}_6)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

known amount of the compound dissolved in 2 N H_2SO_4 was treated with an excess of solid KI. The liberated iodine was titrated with standard sodium thiosulphate solution in 0.2 N acid medium at room temperature using starch solution as an indicator, which required 15.96 equivalents of sodium thiosulphate per mole of the sample corresponding to the reduction of periodate to iodine^{1,2} by the reaction (2)

The potentiometric titration of $Li_7Dy(IO_6)_3 \cdot 3H_2O$ with standard Na_2SO_3 solution shows (Fig. 4) a sharp break at 0.34 volt vs SCE. The volume of Na_2SO_3 solution at this point of inflexion corresponds to 8 equivalents per mole of the complex.

Fig. 4. Potentiometric titration of $Dy(IO_6)_3^{7-}$ with standard sodium sulphite solution.

This indicates the standard potential for $Dy(IO_6)_3^{7-}/Dy^{3+}, I^-$ system. The experimental results (Table 2) are in excellent agreement with the theoretical value and the process of reduction may be represented by the equation (3)

The potential value also indicates that the species $Dy(IO_6)_3^{7-}$ is a strong oxidant.

TABLE 2

Wt. of $Li_7Dy(IO_6)_3 \cdot 3H_2O$	Vol. of sod sulphite soln required (from the curve)	Strength of the sod sulphite soln	Calculated value of $Li_7Dy(IO_6)_3 \cdot 3H_2O$
0.00859 g	60 drops = 3 ml	0.065 N	0.00866 g

That the white and sparingly soluble lithium dysprosium(III) periodate is a complex compound was also established by paper electrophoresis. One drop of the mother liquor i.e., potassium dysprosium periodate was electrophorised using 0.1 N KNO_3

solution as carrier electrolyte applying 200 volt for 1 hr. The paper was cut into two pieces longitudinally, one portion tested with Alizarin-S solution when a red band towards the anode was found and the other was tested for periodate ion with KI solution where a violet band was obtained. It conclusively proved the formation of anionic complex of dysprosium due to the formation of $Dy(IO_6)_3^{7-}$ ion.

Therefore, the structure of the compound $Li_7Dy(IO_6)_3 \cdot 3H_2O$ may be proposed as either Fig. 5a or Fig. 5b.

Fig. 5a

Fig. 5b

In Fig. 5a dysprosium is hexacoordinated while in Fig. 5b it is nine coordinated^{1,4} but iodine is hexacoordinated in both the cases. The exact structure, however, can be revealed by the X-ray diffraction technique.

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